

Peekaboo... I see you

Finding Lyman Continuum Leakers at the Epoch of Reionization

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Reionization:

Escape fraction of Lyman Continuum at $z \sim 1$

Left (red): Rest frame at 1900 Å

Right (blue): Rest frame < 912 Å (Lyman continuum)

Siana et al. 2010

Escape fraction of Lyman Continuum at $z \sim 1$

Siana et al. 2010

Why are leaky starburst galaxies rare?

Low-z Analogs of High-z Starburst Galaxies

Discovery of UV bright galaxies at low redshift ($z=0.1-0.25$) with GALEX

Overview of the properties of LBA galaxies:

- Luminosity $> 2 \times 10^{10} L_{\odot}$
- SFR $\sim 3-50 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$
- Redshift ~ 0.2

Properties similar to Lyman Break Galaxies and hence "Lyman Break Analogs" or LBAs

Heckman et al. 2005, Overzier et al. 2009

Low-z Analogs of High-z Starburst Galaxies

Dominant Central Object (DCO): $\sim 10^9 M_{\odot}$ of stars in ~ 100 pc region

Characterizing Starburst-driven Winds

Heckman & Borthakur 2017

Escape Fraction: Photoelectric Absorption by Hydrogen

Signature of Leaker on their Lyman α : Blue Shifted Emission

Any Emission-line Indicators?

- High flux ratios of the [OIII]5007/[OII]3727 emission-lines.
 - Large ionization parameter \rightarrow ISM optically thin to Lyman continuum

Any other
Indicators?

Radial Ionization Structure for the Strömgen sphere

Another indirect indicator: Weak S II $\lambda 6717, 6731$

Alexandroff et al. 2016

S II arises at the boundary of the Strömgen sphere.

For open HII regions, we expect SII production to reduce but not $H\alpha$

Defining [SII]-deficiency

Revolutionizing Our Knowledge Starburst Galaxies And Reionization: 2020

Lyman α and other emission-lines from starburst galaxies from $z=6$ and beyond

Detecting the first galaxies - $Z \sim 10$ or higher!

Revolutionizing Our Knowledge of Starburst Galaxies And Reionization: 2025

